

TABLE -1
 ANALYTICAL DATA FOR TRIPROPYL TIN DITHIOCARBAMATES (Pr₃Sn₂)

No.	Compounds etc.	Mol. Wt. Found (Calcd.)	B. Pt. (°C) at ~1 mm pressure	Analysis % Found (Calcd.)			Absorption frequencies (cm ⁻¹)	
				Sn	C	H	C-N	C-S
1.	morpholine	380 (410)	170-180	29.06 (29.02)	40.89 (40.98)	7.05 (7.07)	1460 vs 1465 s	1000 vs 1020 s
2.	piperidine	388 (408)	200-205	29.16 (29.17)	44.16 (44.12)	7.58 (7.60)	1449 sd 1460 s	990 } 1005 } ^{br,s}
3.	dibutyl	430 (452)	198-200	26.34 (26.33)	47.72 (47.79)	8.59 (8.63)	1470 sd 1480 s	990 s 1010 w
4.	N-methylaniline	378 (450)	136-38	27.65 (27.67)	47.98 (47.44)	6.76 (6.74)	1455 sd 1460 s	990 s 1005 w
5.	diethyl	372 (396)	—	30.00 (30.05)	42.51 (42.42)	7.86 (7.83)	1481 vs 1460 s	990 } 1000 } ^{s,br}
6.	N-ethylaniline	425 (444)	160-65	26.76 (26.80)	48.69 (48.65)	6.92 (6.98)	1455 s 1460 w	990 s 1020 w

nature of the organic group attached to the nitrogen atom. The substitution of an alkyl group by a heterocyclic group lowers the C-N absorption frequency since the former has high electron releasing capacity while the latter is an electron withdrawing group. The co-ordination behaviour of dithiocarbamate group whether monodentate or bidentate is reflected by C-S stretching absorptions². Presence of two bands at 990 and (1010 ± 10 cm⁻¹) shows the monodentate character of the dithiocarbamate moiety^{1,3}.

In the far infrared region, asym Sn-C and sym Sn-C stretchings have been identified at 590 and 510 cm⁻¹ respectively^{4,5}. The strong intense absorption band at 370 cm⁻¹ is assigned to Sn-S stretching mode of vibration⁶.

The proton magnetic resonance spectra recorded in CDCl₃ show the presence of two groups of signals, one possessing split signals due to N-CH₂ protons at ~ 6-7τ which indicates restricted rotation about C-N bond making the two groups nonequivalent⁷ and thus supporting monodentate character of the dithiocarbamate group⁸. The second group of signal has multiplet at 8.2-9.2τ due to alkyl protons. In the case of compounds containing phenyl ring a multiplet is observed at ~2-3.5τ. The spectra and their integration agree well with the proposed stoichiometry.

The observed stoichiometry coupled with the infrared and proton magnetic resonance spectral data suggest an ester type structure for the newly synthesized compounds possessing a monodentate dithiocarbamate moiety and tetra co-ordinated tin atom.

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Cyclic Coagulation of Surface Waters in Laterite Soils

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IN the place of hackneyed coagulants in water treatment, viz., alum and hydrated coppers and of the costlier polymeric analogues, a new coagulant has been found in MgCO₃ by Thompson *et al.*¹. The chief advantage claimed for this coagulant is the absence of sludge disposal problem. It can be regenerated from the sludge thus ensuring cyclic coagulation².

NOTES

TABLE

Sample No.	Amount of MgCO ₃ (mg/lit)	Amount of Ca(OH) ₂ (mg/lit)	Turbidity	Before Coagulation			After Coagulation			
				pH	Hardness	Alkalinity	Turbidity	pH	Hardness	Alkalinity
1.	13.3	10.7	30	7.5	32.68	19.89	3	7.7	24.88	29.95
2.	20.75	18.6	42	7.5	30.50	21.32	2	8.0	56.63	52.02
3.	16.60	15.0	28	7.4	62.66	41.31	3	7.8	48.90	49.73
4.	18.30	10.7	31	7.6	56.63	55.09	2	7.9	60.99	64.27

Hardness and Alkalinity in mg/lit. of CaCO₃

MgCO₃ in the presence of lime is converted into sparingly soluble Mg(OH)₂ which takes the fine particles in suspension down with it.

Dosage of MgCO₃ required with different characteristics of water have been tabulated¹.

In the present work cyclic coagulation using MgCO₃ was tried on surface waters collected from different ponds used exclusively for potable purposes by the public of Karaikudi. The hardness, pH, alkalinity as well as turbidity were determined both before and after coagulation for each sample. The dosage of MgCO₃ as also the relative amounts of MgCO₃ and Ca(OH)₂ were optimised so as to reduce the residual turbidity to the minimum possible level without causing an undue increase in hardness or alkalinity. The results are tabulated in the following table.

In each of the cases the pH slightly rose up. The pH increase helps recarbonation by lessening the amount of CO₂ needed. pH and alkalinity do not correspond linearly in the tabulated results. This is to be expected as pH is a measure of only H⁺ or OH⁻ concentration while alkalinity takes into account all ions such as OH⁻, CO₃²⁻, HCO₃⁻ and also free CO₂.

Except with sample no. 2 the hardness has not appreciably changed during coagulation. Karaikudi has laterite soil within a few feet depth and in some regions even on the surface. The composition of the soil also varies within a few metres as gauged by the iron content of the laterite. This fact partly explains the non-conformity of sample No. 2 with others in the context of hardness.

Dosage of MgCO₃ is much less than the dosage of alum. The dosage of alum for soft surface waters has been determined by Culp and Culp³ as 20 mg/l. The samples taken up for investigation in the present work are soft as per specifications laid down by the American Water Works Association in 1968⁴. Thus the sample consumes less of MgCO₃ than it would consume alum which is incidentally costlier than MgCO₃.

The work regarding determination of effective pH range for coagulation is under progress.

Experimental

The experimental method followed by us is given

in Chemistry for Sanitary Engineers, Sawyer and McCarty⁵. 300 ml of the sample was taken in a glass jar. Suspensions of MgCO₃ (1 ml = 2.5 mg) and Ca(OH)₂ (1 ml = 1.8 mg) were prepared. The desired amount of coagulant was added to the sample with vigorous stirring. Then the sample was flocculated for 45 min on a paddle stirrer. The sample was allowed to stand and the clear water was analysed for turbidity, pH, hardness and alkalinity. (For turbidity measurements, photo-electric turbidity meter by Toshniwal Instruments, was used).

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Preparation of a Liquid Polysulfide Polymer for Leather Impregnation

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ONE of the most important industrial leathers viz., oil seal leathers is used for a wide variety of purposes in aeroplanes, automobiles and elsewhere as pneumatic or hydraulic packings that are subjected to high pressures and frictional endurance such as air-brakes and hydraulic rams. These leathers should not harden up in hot oil, must be capable of being moulded so that they retain their shape and flexibility at elevated as well as low temperatures. The main property imparted by the impregnant is resistance to hot air, water and hot oils under high pressure as high as 10.5 Kg/cm² and temperatures ranging from 53.9 to 121.1^{°C}.

The common impregnating agents such as tallow and waxes will not stand these stringent requirements resulting in failure of specimens.

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